

The central Chancheng District, Shiwan Street, Zumiao Street, Zhangchu Street, the western Sanshui District, Southwest Street, the eastern Shunde District, London Street, and Leliu Street are where the high value of NQPDE of the road network in Foshan is distributed within the search radius of 1600 meters (Shown in Figure 9). The road coverage of NQPDE high values in the middle road network of Chancheng District increases dramatically as the search radius expands to 3000m, and the proximity of the road network within the town of Nanzhuang in the western part of the region also increases (Shown in Figure 10).

When taking the whole city as the search threshold, in addition to the original areas, NQPDE high-value areas are expanded outward to form high-value proximity areas with "central urban area" "Daliang Ronggui sub-center" and "Fobei sub-center" (Shown in Figure 11). In addition, within the range of this threshold, the road network form of Foshan is as follows: the main structure of high proximity roads, and the extension of medium-low accessibility